

Kinetics of the Acid Hydrolysis of Di-2, 4-Dichlorophenyl Phosphate

M. M. MHALA and S. S. BHATAWDEKAR*

School of Post-graduate Studies and Research in Chemistry, Jiwaji University, Gwalior.

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Investigation for the nucleophilic substitution of di-2, 4-dichlorophenyl phosphate by water has been carried out at 98° in the range 0.005–4.5M HCl, the ester is found to be reactive via conjugate acid species. The rate constants increase with increase in acid concentration and attains optimum value in 3.5M acid. Theoretical rates determined from ionic strength data agree well with the experimentally observed rates. The reaction proceeds with bimolecular nucleophilic attack of water on phosphorus of the conjugate acid species involving P–O fission. The concepts such as kinetic order, Zücker Hammett hypothesis, Bunnet-Olsen's parameters, Arrhenius parameters, solvent effect and solvent isotope effect have been used to give extra support to probable reaction mechanism.

THE survey^{1,2} of kinetics of the diesters shows that very little kinetic study has been carried out, even though diesters are gaining biological importance day to day. In order to solve the problem of complicated biochemical reactions, kinetics of hydrolysis of substituted dibenzyl, diaryl and diallyl esters of phosphoric acid^{3,4} having specific structures have been studied in this school. Generally, diesters of the phosphoric acid found to be least reactive in the series of phosphates⁵. Investigation of the study of di-2,4-dichlorophenyl phosphate, which is a fungicide⁶, was undertaken with a view that the chlorine atoms in ortho and para position of phosphate side chain of the ester may change not only the rate of the hydrolysis but may open new reaction paths.

Materials and Methods: Di-2, 4-dichlorophenyl phosphate was prepared by the method devised by Maguire and Shaw⁷ and was crystallised from chloroform-light petroleum mixture, m. p. 129°–130° (Found-C, 36.94; H, 2.19; P, 8.1; Requires C, 37.1; H, 1.81; P, 7.98).

Procedure: Kinetic runs were carried out at 98° ± 0.05° in the range 0.005–4.5M hydrochloric acid employing 5.0 × 10⁻⁴M solution of di-2, 4-dichlorophenyl phosphate in aqueous-dioxan medium (dioxan-water : 10 : 90 V/V). The rate constants were determined by estimating inorganic phosphate colorimetrically by Allen's method⁸. The hydrolysis of di-2, 4-dichlorophenyl phosphate takes place in two successive steps (1) and (2) which proceed at comparable rates. The analysis of inorganic phosphate measures only the final product from the second step.

If the initial concentration of the diester is represented by D₀, and the concentrations at time 't' of monoester and inorganic phosphate by M and P respectively, then the rate coefficient for the hydrolysis of the diester is given by :

$$k_D = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{D_0}{D_0 - (M + P)}$$

where k_D is the first order rate coefficient for the hydrolysis of the diester.

There is however no convenient method for estimating either phenol or monoester, only the inorganic phosphate can be directly measured. The concentration of the monoester present in an individual run can be evaluated by the Mirror method², using the value of k_M² (rate coefficient for the hydrolysis of monoester), determined by performing simultaneous kinetic runs of the corresponding monoester¹⁰. The first order rate coefficients for the hydrolysis of di-2, 4-dichlorophenyl phosphate determined by mirror method² are shown in Figs. 1, 2, 3.

Constant ionic strength² was maintained using mixtures of sodium chloride and hydrochloric acid. Deuterium oxide (BARC, Trombay) was of 99.4% isotopic purity. Dioxan was purified.⁹ All the chemicals used were of B. D. H. (A. R.) and Riedel quality.

Results and Discussion

The kinetic data of the hydrolysis of di-2, 4-dichlorophenyl phosphate in the region 0.005 to 4.5 M hydrochloric acid shows that the pseudo-first order rate coefficients (Table 1) increase with the increase in acidity upto 2.0 M hydrochloric acid, it appears to be almost constant up to 3.5 M hydrochloric acid and beyond this acidity it decreases (Fig. 1). Unlike benzyl

* Lecture, Department of Chemistry, Govt. Science College, Gwalior.

phosphate, this ester shows bend in strong acid solution. Rise in rate upto maximum in case of aryl phosphates¹⁰ was explained on the basis of complete conversion of substrate into its conjugate acid species. The decrease in rate in strong acid medium has been attributed to ionic strength effect¹¹ and water activity.¹² In this case the decrease in rate beyond 3.5 M hydrochloric acid is probably due to changes in water activity in strong acid medium.

Fig. 1. pH-Log rate profile for the hydrolysis of Di-2,4-dichlorophenyl phosphate at 98°, in the range 0.005 to 4.5M. HCl.

Fig. 2. Acid hydrolysis of Di-2, 4-dichlorophenyl phosphate at constant ionic strength (Temp. 98°).

Kinetic data at constant ionic strength indicate acid catalysis. Plot between rate constants and acid molarities shows that three linear curves with positive slopes meet at origin (Fig. 2). This suggests negligible contribution from hydrolysis via neutral species to the acid catalysed reaction. The conjugate acid species is found to be susceptible to ionic strength effect giving positive salt effect, as the slopes increase with the increase in ionic strength (Fig. 2). Acid catalysed rates and ionic strength are related as

$$\log k_{H^+} \cdot C_{H^+} = \log k_{H_3O^+} + b'_{H^+} \cdot \mu + \log C_{H^+}$$

The theoretical rates computed from the second empirical term of Debye-Huckel equation¹³ have been found to be in close agreement with those experimentally observed (Table 1) upto 2.0 M hydrochloric acid. After 2.0 M hydrochloric acid calculated rates agree well with the observed rates by applying water activity, and the rate is represented by the equation

$$k_e = k_{H^+} \cdot C_{H^+} (a_{H_2O})^n$$

Bimolecularity of the acid catalysed reaction in moderately strong acid solution has been supported, using Zücker Hammett hypothesis¹⁴. The slope, 1.06 of the linear plot between log rate coefficients and log acidities (Fig. 3) which is nearly unity, confirms the bimolecular⁹ nature of the reaction.

Fig. 3. Acid hydrolysis of Di-2, 4-dichlorophenyl phosphate at 98° (Zücker-Hammett hypothesis.)

TABLE 1—CALCULATED AND OBSERVED RATES FOR THE HYDROLYSIS OF DI-2, 4-DICHLOROPHENYL PHOSPHATE AT 98°.

HCl M	Observed rates $10^3 k_e \text{ min.}^{-1}$	Calculated rates
0.006	0.014	0.012*
0.01	0.025	0.026
0.05	0.125	0.129
0.1	0.292	0.262
0.5	1.588	1.410
1.0	3.128	3.090
1.5	5.081	5.080
2.0	7.519	7.44
2.5	7.745	7.970
3.0	8.240	8.270
3.5	10.950	11.490
4.0	6.889	6.270
4.5	7.981	8.000

* Calculated by mirror method.²

Bunnett-Olsen's parameters ϕ , the slope of the plot between $\log k_e + H_0$ and $C_{H^+} + H_0$, has been shown to be suitable to explain the acid dependence on the reaction rate of dinitrophenyl phosphate¹⁵ ($\phi = 1.2$). Similar result is also observed for di-2, 4-dichlorophenyl phosphate (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Bunnett & Olsen's plot for the hydrolysis of Di-2,4, dichlorophenyl phosphate in aqueous HCl at 98°

Bimolecular nature of the reaction should result in high negative entropy of activation and comparatively small activation energy¹⁶. Arrhenius parameters¹⁶ for the hydrolysis of di-2, 4-dichlorophenyl phosphate have been calculated in 2.5 and 4.5 M hydrochloric acid (2.5 M HCl : E=16.6 K. cal/mole, A=8.1×10⁵ sec⁻¹, $\Delta S^\ddagger = -33.9$ e.u., 4.5 M HCl : E=16.0 K. cal/mole, A=3.6×10⁵ sec⁻¹, $\Delta S^\ddagger = -35.6$ e.u.) at different temperatures 80°, 90° and 98° for knowing the reaction mechanism on both sides of the maximum and found to be of bimolecular range.

Theory of solvent effect put forward by Hughes and Ingold¹⁷ has been used for knowing the nature of transition state. Decrease in rate with the increase in ionizing power of the solvent (Table 2) in case of the hydrolysis of di-2, 4-dichlorophenyl phosphate shows dispersion of the charge in the transition state.

TABLE 2—THE INFLUENCE OF THE SOLVENT ON THE HYDROLYSIS OF 2, 4-DICHLOROPHENYL PHOSPHATE IN AQUEOUS HYDROCHLORIC ACID SOLUTION AT 98°.

Acid (HCl) M	Percentage of dioxan (V/V)	$k_e \times 10^3$ min. ⁻¹
0.1	10	0.292
3.1	30	0.61
0.1	50	0.89
0.1	60	1.18
2.5	10	7.745
2.5	30	8.67
2.5	50	13.47
4.0	10	6.889
4.0	50	7.39

Chart. Mechanism of the acid hydrolysis of Di-2, 4-dichlorophenyl phosphate.

Solvent isotope effect in 2 M hydrochloric acid by change over from dioxan-water to dioxan-D₂O ($k_{D_2O}/k_{H_2O} = 1.05$) favours the formation of conjugate acid species by a fast pre-equilibrium proton transfer^{1,8}.

Phosphorus-oxygen bond fission of the conjugate acid species of the ester is expected to be more probable during hydrolysis due to formation of resonance stabilised phenoxide ion. Such a P-O bond fission will be facilitated by the electron attracting chlorine substituents. The phosphorus-oxygen fission is further indicated from the comparative kinetic data of similar phosphates.⁴

On the basis of experimental evidences the probable reaction paths for the acid hydrolysis of di-2, 4-dichlorophenyl phosphate may be formulated as shown in chart. This is followed by the hydrolysis of monoester into inorganic phosphate¹⁰.

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